

New analogous progesterone haptens and their A/B ring conformation : Determination of dihedral angles using extended Karplus equations[†]

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The specificity of progesterone action largely depends on the conformation of its ring A in solution. Selectivity and specificity of haptens for immunoassay is dependent on their conformational similarity to that of the parent molecule. Conformational distortions due to bulky substituents have often led to a loss in activity. Therefore, determination of conformation of the steroidal rings has always been an area of high intrinsic interest. Conformational analysis of the A/B rings of the synthesized steroid hormone derivatives, viz. 16 α -methylprogesterone, 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -methylprogesterone, 16 α -methylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione, 16 α -ethylprogesterone, 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -ethylprogesterone, 16 α -ethylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione, 16 α -prop-2'-enylprogesterone, 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -prop-2'-enylprogesterone, 16 α -prop-2'-enylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione has been carried out using high resolution 1D proton NMR spectra. Calculations are carried out by employing three of the latest extensions to the Karplus equations, viz. those suggested by Colucci, Osawa and Barfield. The A ring conformations of these steroids are determined by calculating dihedral angles of the ethane fragments consisting of C1-C2 and C6-C7 from the vicinal coupling constants derived from high field ¹H NMR spectra of the hormone derivatives. The dihedral angle θ could not be calculated directly since the nature of the equations is not truly quadratic. A program has been devised wherein the calculated *J* value has to be fitted to the observed *J* value for each of the Colucci, Osawa and Barfield equations. Molecular modeling of the 4-en-3-one steroid hormone derivatives has also been carried out using MM2 calculations.

During the synthesis of steroidal haptens, a steroid has to undergo several functional changes. That these changes are vulnerable to conformational transmission is well known¹⁻³. Principal conformational variations in most naturally occurring steroid hormones involve rings A and B⁴⁻⁶. Androgens, progestins and corticoids possess a 4-en-3-one moiety in their A ring which forms the area of conformational flexibility. Ring B is the focal point of activity in cholestanes and estrogens. Ring A conformations in steroids have been considered to exert significant influence on the receptor binding ability. A correlation has also been noted between the bowing of ring A towards the α face and the variation in the antiinflammatory activity in a series of fluorocorticosteroids⁷. Selectivity and specificity of haptens for immunoassay is dependent on their conformational similarity to that of the parent molecule. Conformational distortions due to bulky substituents have often led to a loss in activity^{8,9}. Therefore, determination of conformation of the steroidal rings has always been an area of high intrinsic interest. Study of the conformations of the newly synthesized alkylated progesterones and the haptens would offer a gravity of their potential as haptens¹⁰⁻¹³.

The 4-en-3-one steroids have been subjected to conformational analysis several times through X-ray investigations as well as solution studies. Early X-ray reports by Duax *et al.* suggested that in crystal, steroids display both, sofa and

half-chair conformations for ring A. 2 β -Substitutions cause A ring inversions and that unsaturation at C-5 resulted in a flattened ring A¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

In the present report, conformational analysis of the A/B rings of the steroid hormone derivatives, viz. 16 α -methylprogesterone (1C), 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -methylprogesterone (1E), 16 α -methylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione (1D), 16 α -ethylprogesterone (2C), 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -ethylprogesterone (2E), 16 α -ethylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione (2D), 16 α -prop-2'-enylprogesterone (3C), 6 β -hydroxy-16 α -prop-2'-enylprogesterone (3E) and 16 α -prop-2'-enylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-trione (3D), which were prepared by oxidizing the respective 16 α -alkylpregnenolones 1A, 2A and 3A, has been carried out using high resolution 1D proton NMR spectra. Dihedral angles have been calculated by applying improvised Karplus equations suggested by Colucci, Osawa and Barfield. Molecular modeling of the 4-en-3-one steroid hormone derivatives has also been carried out using MM2 calculations. The dihedral angles obtained from the energy minimized structures were comparable with the computed dihedral angles.

Results and Discussion

16 α -Alkylprogesterone analogs, viz. 1C, 1E, 1D, 2C, 2E, 2D, 3C, 3E and 3D were synthesized by the PCC oxidation of the respective 16 α -alkylpregnenolones 1A, 2A and 3A (Fig. 1)¹⁸.

[†] Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

Fig. 1

The A ring conformations of these steroids were determined by calculating dihedral angles of the ethane fragments consisting of C1-C2 and C6-C7 from the vicinal coupling constants derived from high field ¹H NMR spectra of the hormone derivatives. Calculations were carried out by employing three of the latest extensions to the Karplus equations, viz. those suggested by Colucci, Osawa and Barfield¹⁹⁻²¹. The Colucci and the Osawa extensions have taken into account the substituent effects whereas the Barfield extension has taken into account the internal C-C-H angles.

In order to calculate the dihedral angles, it was essential to represent C1-C2 and C6-C7 ethane fragments of the steroids in a Newman projection form with a 60° angle between the two protons under consideration. Substituents to these fragments were then numbered in a clockwise direction, those on the carbon in front followed by those on the

Colucci's equation (1) :

$$J = -4 \cos \theta [\cos (\theta - 120) (\zeta_1 J_1 + \zeta_4 J_4) + \cos (\theta + 120) (\zeta_2 J_2 + \zeta_3 J_3)] + A \{1 + 4 \cos \theta [\cos (\theta - 120) (\zeta_1 + \zeta_4) + \cos (\theta + 120) (\zeta_2 + \zeta_3)]\} + B \cos \theta + C \cos 2\theta$$

Osawa's equation (2) :

$$J = A \cos \theta + B \cos 2\theta + W E \cos \theta \sum \Delta \kappa_i \cos \theta_i +$$

$$H \left[\left(\frac{1+2}{2} \right) - 110 \right] + M$$

Barfield equation (3) :

$$J(\phi_1, \phi_2, \theta) = 23.8 a(\phi_1, \phi_2) \cos^2 \theta + [1370.4 b_1(\phi_1, \phi_2) + 587.6 b_2(\phi_1, \phi_2) + 906.1 b_3(\phi_1, \phi_2)] \cos \theta + 0.9$$

$$a(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (1 + \cos \phi_1)(1 + \cos \phi_2)$$

$$b_1(\phi_1, \phi_2) = [\cot(\phi_1/2) \cot(\phi_2/2)] [\cos \phi_1 \cos \phi_2]$$

$$b_2(\phi_1, \phi_2) = [\cot(\phi_1/2) \cot(\phi_2/2)] [\cos \phi_1 \cos \phi_2]^{1/2}$$

$$b_3(\phi_1, \phi_2) = [\cot(\phi_1/2) \cot(\phi_2/2)] [\cos \phi_2 (-\cos \phi_1)^{1/2} + \cos \phi_1 (-\cos \phi_2)^{1/2}]$$

carbon behind. Once these substituents were assigned correct numbers, appropriate substituent constants were inserted into the respective equations (Equations 1-3). The dihedral angle θ could not be calculated directly since the nature of the equations was not truly quadratic. A program was devised wherein the calculated J value had to be fitted to the observed J value for each of the Colucci, Osawa and Barfield equations. This was done by incrementing the dihedral angle by 1/100th of a degree starting from 0° to 360° and calculat-

Table 1. Comparison of dihedral angles in 16 α -alkylprogesteroes*

Compd. substituent	1C					2C					3C				
	J	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	J	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	J	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H
1 α -2 α	5.7	-50	-50	-50	-50	5.1	-53	-54	-52	-50	5.4	-51	-52	-51	-50
1 α -2 β	13.8	-152	-	-	-168	13.8	-152	-	-	-168	13.8	-152	-	-	-168
1 β -2 α	3.3	-	53	62	64	3.0	-	56	64	64	3.0	-	56	64	64
1 β -2 β	4.5	-54	-32	-56	-53	4.5	-54	-32	-56	-53	4.8	-68	-30	-54	-53
6 α -7 α	4.8	54	30	54	59	4.5	55	32	55	58	4.8	54	30	54	58
6 α -7 β	2.4	-	-66	-	-58	2.4	-	-66	-	-58	2.7	-	-62	-66	-58
6 β -7 α	12.9	152	-	-	174	12.9	152	-	-	174	12.9	152	-	-	174
6 β -7 β	5.7	50	49	49	58	5.7	50	49	49	57	5.7	50	49	49	57

* J = Coupling constant, θ_C = dihedral angle from Colucci equation, θ_O = dihedral angle from Osawa equation, θ_B = dihedral angle from Barfield equation, θ_H = dihedral angle from energy minimized structure.

Table 2. Comparison of dihedral angles in 6 β -hydroxy-16 β -alkylprogesterones*

Compd. substituent	1E					2E					3E				
	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H
1 α -2 α	4.8	-54	-57	-54	-50	4.8	-54	-57	-54	-50	4.8	-54	-57	-54	-50
1 α -2 β	14.4	-153	-	-	-168	14.7	-154	-	-	-168	14.7	-154	-	-	-168
1 β -2 α	2.7	-	59	66	64	2.7	-	59	66	64	3.0	-	56	64	64
1 β -2 β	4.8	-52	-30	-54	-53	5.1	-51	-28	-52	-58	4.8	-52	-30	-54	-53
6 α -7 α	2.7	58	-	66	56	3.3	55	-	62	56	2.7	58	-	66	55
6 α -7 β	2.7	-	-	-66	-60	2.4	-	-	-	-60	2.7	-	-	-66	-60

*Explanation same as in Table 1.

Table 3. Comparison of dihedral angles in 16 α -alkylpregn-4-en-3,6,20-triones*

Compd. substituent	1D					2D					3D				
	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H	<i>J</i>	θ_C	θ_O	θ_B	θ_H
1 α -2 α	5.4	-51	-52	-51	-47	5.7	-50	-50	-50	-47	5.7	-50	-50	-50	-47
1 α -2 β	14.1	-153	-	-	-164	13.8	-152	-	-	-164	14.1	-153	-	-	-164
1 β -2 α	2.4	-	62	68	68	2.7	-	59	66	68	2.7	-	59	66	68
1 β -2 β	5.1	-51	-28	-52	-48	4.8	-52	-30	-54	-48	5.1	-51	-28	-52	-48
7 α -8 β	12.2	-	-	178	172	12.3	-	-	178	172	12.2	-	-	178	172

*Explanation same as in Table 1.

ing the coupling constant for each increment. Those dihedral angles which resulted in a coupling constant value equal to that observed were picked. Four values of θ for the four quadrants were obtained for each calculation. Only one of these dihedral angle values was found to be stereochemically sensible to make a ball and stick model and this value was considered to be the correct value (Tables 1–3).

The progesterone analogs were also subjected to minimization of energy employing MM2 calculations²². Dihedral angles of the C1-C2 and C6-C7 ethane fragments in the minimized structures were accrued and compared with the calculated ones.

The dihedral angle calculations in case of the synthesized steroidal 4-en-3-ones showed that the 1 α -H, in the 16 α -alkylated progesterones, formed a torsion angle of nearly 180° with 2 β -H while with 2 α -H it formed an angle of 50°. 1 β -H was poised at an angle of *ca.* 54° with 2 α -H while the dihedral angle between 1 α and 2 α protons was *ca.* 50°. These dihedral angle values confirmed that the A ring in 16 α -alkylated progesterones was a normal 1 α ,2 β -half-chair. The dihedral angle between 6 α -H and 7 α -H was nearly 54° while that between 6 α -H and 7 β -H was *ca.* 66°. This suggested that the B ring in all these cases existed in a normal chair conformation.

In 16 α -alkylated-6 β -hydroxyprogesterones, dihedral angles between the C-1 and C-2 protons were similar to those observed in the former case. Hence, in the present case also, ring A is likely to exist in a normal half-chair

conformation. Dihedral angle calculations indicated an angle of *ca.* 58° between 6 α -H and 7 α -H while that between 6 α -H and 7 β -H was also of the same order. This suggested a normal chair conformation for the B ring of the alkylated 6 β -hydroxyprogesterones. Both, the A as well as B ring conformations corroborated with those in the energy minimized structures of the corresponding steroids.

Optimized conformations for the alkylated pregn-4-en-3,6,20-triones showed that they contained flattened A and B rings where C-3, C-4, C-5, C-6, C-7 and C-10 existed in one plane. The A ring was as usual in the normal half-chair conformation with C-1 lying below and C-2 lying above the plane. Ring B was found to be flattened due to the presence of 6-oxo group which was indicated by the decrease in $J_{7\alpha-8\beta}$ (12.2 Hz). Consequently, the dihedral angle between the two protons also decreased (*ca.* 166°) causing a flattening at C-5–C-6–C-7. Thus, ring B also existed in a half-chair conformation (Fig. 2).

Conclusion :

The newly synthesized alkylated progesterones were analyzed for the conformation of their A/B ring system. Dihedral angles for the synthesized steroid hormone derivatives have been calculated by three different equations and compared with those obtained from molecular modeling of these structures for optimum geometries. The results showed that in some cases the values obtained from the three equations were marginally different while in some other cases there were discrepancies upto 20°. Thus the comparison with

Fig. 2

MM2 energy minimized structures suggested that the three techniques were complementary to each other and could be satisfactorily used to determine the steroidal ring conformations. There was no significant change in the conformation of ring A which existed as a normal half-chair whereas ring B possessed a slightly distorted chair conformation due to Δ^4 . Molecular modeling studies showed that the dihedral angles between vicinal protons of ring A and ring B in the energy minimized structures were comparable to those obtained through empirical calculations from coupling constants between the respective protons. This study confirmed that the haptens were indeed similar in conformation to the parent steroid hormone, progesterone.

Experimental

The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AM 500 and Varian VXR 300S spectrometers (with digital resolution 0.16 Hz). The spectra were referenced with tetramethylsilane as 0.0 ppm for ^1H NMR and the central line of CDCl_3 was set to 77.0 ppm for ^{13}C NMR. ^1H - ^1H COSY experiments were performed in absolute intensity mode on a Varian VXR 300S spectrometer with 256 t_1 increments and data size 512W for acquisition. Homonuclear phase sensitive NOESY experiments were performed on a Varian VXR 300S spectrometer with mixing time of 1 s. HMQC experiments were performed on a Bruker AM 500 spectrometer.

The molecular modeling system used was Hyperchem Release 3 for Windows Serial No. 510-10005096 wherein energy minimizations were carried out using MM2 calculations.

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